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STORIES DRAWN FROM THE MOTIFS OF THE EPIC KITABI-DƏDƏ QORQUD

Abstract

The stories that hold a significant place in Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə's artistic prose are primarily gathered in the collections *At Dawn*, *The Swan Lake*, and *From Generations to Generations*. The writer's stories stand out for their richness of content, artistic depth, smooth and expressive language. These stories attract attention with their brevity, natural flow, and artistic weight, which stem from the traditions of oral folk literature.

The smooth narrative technique, vivid imagery, and conciseness are some of the qualities that characterize stories written over different years, including *A Leaf from the Plane Tree*, *The Lights Came On*, *In the Camp*, *Groundless Fears*, *Guarding Beauty*, *The Hawk*, *Namesakes*, *The Light of Dawn*, *Babak's Oath*, and *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower*.

The stories *The Hawk*, *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower*, and *Babak's Oath* are among the writer's artistic achievements. It is well known that oral folk literature has served as a rich source of inspiration for many literary figures. The most powerful representatives of Azerbaijani literature have drawn from the wellspring of oral folk creativity to produce invaluable works of art. Similarly, Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə's stories are closely tied to oral folk literature. In his stories, the writer has drawn on folk creativity, infused many folkloric motifs with new meaning and content, and created remarkable literary works that resonate with the modern era. These works play an important role in instilling moral values in children and in developing their language skills.

This article focuses on the stories included in Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə's book *The Power of the People*, which are entirely based on the episodes and plots of *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*. The stories in the book are presented under three headings: *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower*, *The Power of the People*, and *The Mad Ozan*. The story *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower* is based on the episode *Dirsə Khan's Son Buğac*, *The Power of the People* is based on *The Plundering of Qazan Khan's Home*, and *The Mad Ozan* is based on the episode of *Bamsı Beyrək* from *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*.

The section titled *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower* consists of seven stories: *The Hero's Name*; *The Slanderer*; *The Hunt*; *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower*; *The Messenger*; *A Father's Love*; *Life for Life*, *Blood for Blood*. The story *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower* tells of Azerbaijan's heroic past, the patriotism of Oghuz warriors, their struggle against treacherous enemies, and the immense power of maternal love. Themes of devotion to the homeland, mother-child affection, and the fight against the enemy hold a central place in the story.

Overall, in these stories based on the episodes of *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*, the author emphasizes conveying to the younger generation the historical destiny, struggles, geographical position, economic life, family customs, and linguistic heritage of the Azerbaijani people — all closely tied to this magnificent monument, which for a long time had been wrongly attributed to other nations, but in fact belongs to the *Oğuznamə* cycle of Azerbaijani epics.

Keywords: episode, epic, folklore, motif, ozan, plot, story

Introduction

In 20th-century Azerbaijani children's literature, just as in the field of poetry, there were also writers who worked with the same intensity and creativity in prose. When speaking of these artists, two names and literary personalities immediately come to mind: Abdulla Shaig and Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə!

Although Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə began his literary career with poetry, the plots and events within his poetic narratives stand out for their situational character. This distinctive feature became one of the notable qualities that manifests itself in both his poems and narrative poems. In this sense, one can truly consider poetry and prose as two wings of his creative output as an artist. Engaging in literary activity across both genres endowed his creative legacy with a sense of universality. This alternation and interchange between the two genres can be consistently and systematically traced throughout the more than sixty years of his literary career.

As a children's writer, Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə was one of those talented authors who skillfully drew upon myths, legends, and tales—the products of ancient beliefs—as well as the plots and motifs of folk narratives and epics. When reflecting on the reasons why Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə often turned to historical themes, particularly to folk plots and motifs, the first thing that comes to mind is his prioritization of patriotism—an essential theme that was ultimately aimed at educating the younger generation and shaping their character. This goal is clearly felt in his works. (11, p. 66)

As an artist, starting from the 1940s, he penned numerous works including *The Long and the Short*, *The Lark's Song*; *Dozanqurdu and Other Insects*; *A Lion's Heart*; *Contemplation*; *Panegyric*; *The Painter and the Ruler*; *Sleeping Potion*; *The Little Frog*; *Friendship*; and *The Water of Life*. In these poems, as well as in his narrative poems such as *Tale*, *The Naughty Little Goat*, and *Sweet Spring*, one can clearly see the elements and features of the epic genre within folklore.

A different approach to folklore. Of course, "it should also be taken into account that the overwhelming majority of writers working in the field of children's literature have, to some extent, chosen the literary forms and genres belonging to folklore as their creative credo, and this choice is by no means accidental." (10, p.19) This is because, from the very moment a child enters the world, their psychology and development are inevitably intertwined with and exposed to folklore. Without doubt, such interaction plays a crucial role in nurturing noble human qualities in children — fostering a sense of courage, honesty, respect for elders, and compassion for the younger ones. Naturally, love for parents and homeland, respect and reverence for national values were also among the core themes and literary-aesthetic goals transmitted from folklore texts into written literary works.

People's Writer, academician, and Hero of Socialist Labor, Mirzə İbrahimov, once commented on the contributions of Abdulla Shaig, one of the prominent literary figures of children's literature and a well-known pedagogue. When evaluating Shaig's contributions to both poetry and prose for children, İbrahimov wrote:

"Abdulla Shaig's contributions to the development of Azerbaijani children's and youth literature are immense. As a brilliant teacher who deeply understood child psychology and as the founder of the renowned 'Shaig School,' which raised hundreds of talented young people, Shaig's works written for children have, thanks to their naturalness, psychological depth, beauty and fluency of language, and the vividness and wholeness of their characters, been beloved by generations — works that were cherished in the past and continue to be regarded as shining examples of our children's literature today." (6, p.9)

Without doubt, in the period following Abdulla Shaig's death — from 1959 to 1984 — one of the writers who uniquely continued and developed both of these creative directions was none other than Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə.

Naturally, among the writers who produced fine examples of children's prose, the works of People's Writers Süleyman Rəhimov and Əli Vəliyev, as well as specialized children's writers such as Nəriman Süleymanov, Əli Səmədli, and Baba Həsənov, displayed a pronounced and active interest in this field. As was noted, İsa Hümətov and Əzizə Əhmədova also demonstrated similar qualities in their stories. In the field of science fiction for children, the contributions of Emin

Mahmudov and Natiq Abdullayev deserve special mention. In the works of both these authors — who richly drew upon the epic heritage of Azerbaijani oral folklore — one can clearly observe this creative tendency.

When discussing Süleyman Rəhimov's stories in this vein, critic Qulu Xəlilov once noted, in his analytical article *The Artist with the Mountainous Stature*, the prominent place of folklore in Rəhimov's work:

"Just as some of his stories were masterfully crafted, his fables, legends, and stories written for children also reveal another dimension of his talent as a

writer. In his separately published books such as *The Fairy's Pebble* (1959), *The Laughing Fish* (1964), and *Gülsabah* (1968), the author draws upon folkloric motifs to paint colorful and captivating pictures of the children's world. The author uses folklore as a source — a creative wellspring — enriching its educational value with a contemporary spirit and presenting it vividly to his readers. These works, collected under the headings 'Fables' and 'Legends,' once again showcase the writer's ability to create lively, authentic scenes, his deep knowledge of folk literature, his sharp sense of humor and satire, his overall writing talent, and his profound understanding of life and humanity." (7, p.115)

As a writer, Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə must undoubtedly be recognized as standing among these prominent names, while at the same time demonstrating a unique approach to folklore and an individualized style of drawing from it. This is most clearly visible in his conscious and deliberate reference to epic motifs and plots, where his distinctive literary stance emerges.

Stories written based on the epic "Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud". The series of stories written by Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə based on the magnificent epic *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud* is significant not only as an example of the author's creative engagement with its plots and motifs, but also for reasons far beyond simple adaptation or borrowing. What makes this approach particularly noteworthy is its role in publicly reclaiming and reaffirming the ownership of this monumental cultural treasure — an epic belonging to the *Oğuznamə* cycle, which, for a long time, had been falsely attributed to other nations, hidden behind a veil of prohibitions. These stories serve as a deliberate effort to instill in younger generations an awareness of the epic's connection to the historical fate, struggles, geographical identity, economic life, family traditions, and language of the Azerbaijani people — fostering a sense of ownership and pride in these ethno-cultural values.

In fact, the principle of historicism stands out as one of the core creative features in Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə's engagement with folklore themes. The stories he wrote based on the episodes of *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud* are particularly notable for how they embody and highlight the historical meaning and essence embedded within the original epic.

It must be emphasized from the outset that these stories draw their inexhaustible wellspring of ideas and content from individual episodes of the epic itself, immersing the reader into the semilegendary, semi-historical realities of ancient millennia. In this sense, it is indeed true that:

"From ancient times onward, *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud* has spoken of life and death, loyalty and betrayal, love and hatred, bravery and cowardice, good and evil. Generations have passed, eras have changed, but when *Dədə Qorqud* declared, 'Oh my beautiful, my khan, what have I told you?'

— the wisdom in his words remained as fresh as ever." (10, p.18)

The fact that these stories were written at a time when the strict prohibitions on *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud* were partially lifted was, undoubtedly, a progressive

literary event. It is particularly important to note that after the epic was first published in 1939 under the editorship of academician Həmid Araslı, selected passages from it were made accessible to Azerbaijani literary and scholarly circles. This created wide-ranging opportunities for younger students and youth to fully absorb and appreciate this masterpiece of heroism and bravery. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that at a period when debates over the epic's origins were still unresolved, adapting select passages into stories served the dual purpose of both promoting and popularizing the epic.

Existing research confirms that the first such initiative in 20th-century Azerbaijani prose was undertaken by Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə. The stories collected in his book *The Power of the People* are entirely based on the episodes and plots of *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*. The stories in the book are presented under three section titles:

- A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower
- The Power of the People
- The Mad Ozan

The section *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower* consists of seven stories: *The Name of the Hero*; *The Slanderer*; *The Hunt*; *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower*; *The Messenger*; *A Father's Love*; *Life for Life, Blood for Blood*

The first story in this section, *The Name of the Hero*, opens with a vibrant depiction of the awakening of spring. The breath of spring fills the valleys, plains, and meadows clothed in green; the sound of rushing waters echoes far and wide, and the roaring rivers spread the freshness and energy of the season to all, bringing with it a sense of life and emotion that finds its way into the reader's heart.

At the spring festival organized by Bayındır Khan, the khan of all khans, the gathering of famed warriors — heroes renowned for their bravery and legendary deeds — sets the scene. These warriors, as occasion demands, proudly display their strength and prowess in front of all, creating scenes that perfectly capture the festive spirit and atmosphere of spring.

The most memorable event in the story is, naturally, the scene where a bull, held in chains by three men on its right and three men on its left, breaks free and charges into the arena, filling the spectators with a sense of excitement and suspense. Suddenly, a fifteen-year-old youth leaps into the arena, and after an intense struggle, he manages to overpower the bull and cut off its head. This moment instantly marks him as a hero. The hero is then summoned to appear before the khan, where he reveals that he is Dirsə Khan's son. He also tells the khan that he does not yet have a name. Finally, in recognition of his bravery, Dədə Qorqud bestows upon him the name Buğac, bringing the story to a remarkable and symbolic conclusion.

The celebration of spring, the scene where Buğac tames the bull, and the poetic lines uttered by Dədə Qorqud while naming him all blend harmoniously with the overall content of the story. This organic integration of poetic speech into the prose text stands out as a particularly innovative touch.

In the story titled *The Slanderer* (Cuğul), the main plot revolves around the chief steward of Dirsə Khan,

who, envious of Buğac's growing fame and strength, falsely accuses him. The steward manipulates events to convince the khan to order Buğac's execution. In the story titled *The Hunt* (Ov), Buğac is shot with an arrow by his own father. In the story *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower*, Buğac's mother sets out to search for her son. When she finds him, wounded and helpless, she nurses him back to health using her own milk and a medicinal mountain flower. The power of maternal love takes center stage in this story.

The story *A Mother's Heart – A Mountain Flower* speaks of our people's heroic past, the patriotism of the Oghuz warriors, their fierce struggle against treacherous enemies, and the overwhelming strength of maternal love. The themes of devotion to the homeland, mother-child love, and the fight against the enemy form the core of the story. At the heart of the story stands the figure of Buğac — the valiant son of the nation. In archery and horseback riding, he has no equal. At the same time, Buğac is brave, wise, and resourceful.

Buğac's bravery at the public festival, his courage in defeating the raging bull in the arena, and his success in saving the people from danger bring joy and pride to his parents and friends alike. The Khan of khans praises Buğac's heroism, and the elder of the people, Dədə Qorqud, arrives to give him his name and offer his blessing.

In the story, the hostile forces are represented by Yasovulbaş (the Chief Steward) and his followers. Driven by his ambition to seize power, Yasovulbaş schemes to eliminate Buğac. He convinces the khan that Buğac has betrayed his own father and is plotting to kill him. The aging khan falls for the enemy's deception and issues the order for his son's execution.

For many years, Anaxatun, who had lived with the longing for a child, now takes pride in her son Buğac's bravery and courage. The mother impatiently awaits her son's return from the hunt. However, when she does not see her son among those returning, she is overcome with deep distress and asks the khan:

"My heart is breaking, khan — speak, tell me, where is my child? I will tear apart steep mountains with my bare hands to find my son! I will hold back wild and raging floods with my chest to save my son! I will bite and shred lions and wolves with my own teeth to rescue my son! Until my fiery breath is extinguished, until my body burns to ash, I will never give up on my son, khan! Where is my lion, where is my Buğac?"

Buğac, unaware of the enemy's deception, cannot even imagine that his own father could be led to plot against him. His feelings toward his father, his readiness to sacrifice his life for the sake of his homeland and his people, and his determination to avenge himself against traitors are all vividly and emotionally depicted in the story.

In the story titled *The Messenger* (Çapar), the central event is the moment when a spy conveys the news to the Chief Steward (Yasovulbaş) that Buğac — believed to be dead — is actually alive and well. The story also describes how Yasovulbaş orchestrates the looting and plundering of the palace treasury, culminating in the following scene: "Having lost all strength, the khan

had become indifferent to everything, offering no resistance. They bound him with a rope, secured him to a horse, and set off on their way." (2, p.267). The story also recounts the steward's final treacherous act — handing over the aging khan to the enemy king. The story *A Father's Love* (*Ata Sevgisi*) contains Buğac's recollections of his childhood and memories related to his father. The final story in this section, *Life for Life, Blood for Blood* (*Cana-can, Qana-qan*), portrays Buğac's tireless efforts to rescue his father from the clutches of the enemy, motivated by the deep love of a devoted son.

The stories described in detail above were all written based on the episode *Dirsa Khan's Son Buğac* from *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud*. These stories achieve notable artistic merit by weaving together the events, heroic feats, and acts of espionage with rich descriptions of nature, creating a unified and harmonious whole.

"In order to enhance the readability of the stories, the author provides extensive descriptions of nature. In the original epic, descriptions of nature serve as a powerful backdrop to the unfolding events." (9, p.86)

The section *The Power of the People* (*El Gücü*) includes the following stories: *The Black Worry*; *The Raid*; *The Black Shepherd*; *Mother and Son*; *The Khan and the Shepherd*; *The Power of the People*.

The story *The Black Worry* recounts Khan Qazan's desire to go hunting and the events that unfold during the hunt. In these stories, the author's tendency to change the locations where the events take place, deviating somewhat from the original episodes in the epic, is also noticeable. In fact, replacing the original settings in the storyline with alternative locations is always a creative experiment whose success can never be guaranteed.

A clear example of this approach can be found in the section *The Mad Ozan*, where the events are presented under new and original titles and headings that do not appear in the original *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud* episodes.

Conclusion. The discussions surrounding the genre classification of the stories Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə wrote based on the plots and motifs of *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud* have sparked considerable debate. The author himself correctly refers to these works as stories and explicitly labels them as "Stories Based on the Episodes of *Dədə Qorqud*" on the title page of his book.

Doctor of Philological Sciences Yeganə İsmayılova, in her monograph *The Book of Dədə Qorqud and Modern Azerbaijani Literary Thought*, evaluates

Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə's creative efforts in this direction and writes: "The conclusion that the first prose works based on certain episodes (or multiple episodes) of the *Kitabi-Dədə Qorqud* epic were created by Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə reflects the truth." (11)

The series of stories, penned by the author in a simple and accessible language suited to children's psychology, and inspired by the content, ideas, and artistic qualities of the magnificent monument from the *Oğuznamə* cycle, reveal the potential for transforming historicism into a significant vehicle for modern literary and aesthetic thought.

The research also places particular emphasis on the qualities and nuances that Mikayıl Rzaquluzadə introduced into the structure, themes, plots, and narrative techniques of both his prose works and narrative poems, demonstrating his ability to skillfully draw from the rich treasure trove of Azerbaijani oral folk literature. This ability is identified as a tangible manifestation of his craftsmanship, established directly through analysis of the literary text itself.

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